

Example Data Management Plan – concise version

Understanding patient symptoms, thoughts and experiences of hyperemesis gravidarum during antenatal and postnatal periods

Data Stewardship Wizard (DSW) Example Data Management Plan

Concise version

Organisation
ELIXIR-UK

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Based on

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I. Data areas and data types

This study will generate qualitative data from questionnaires and interviews, in addition to semi-quantitative HELP (HyperEmesis Level Prediction) score data. Interview data will be collected as audio but will ultimately be transcribed automatically using software. We will generate metadata and associated documentation such as electronic participant consent forms, distress protocol(s), interim reports and statistical analyses. All data will be pseudonymised and the pseudonymisation key will be kept in a separate location, accessible only to the project PI. We anticipate that we will generate approximately 50 GB of data over the project's lifetime.

II. Standards and metadata

We will generate and maintain detailed metadata describing all aspects of our methodology, including data collection, inclusion/exclusion criteria, data cleansing and statistical analyses. Questionnaire data will use controlled vocabularies and established coding schemas where possible and we will create a data dictionary to describe all variables. For interview data, we will follow the 'Consolidated criteria for reporting qualitative research' (COREQ) standards to ensure maximal metadata capture.

III. Relationship to other data available in public repositories

This study will generate novel primary data. Where possible, we will use existing related datasets from published literature within the field for comparison and verification of findings.

IV. Secondary use

We anticipate that this data will be of particular interest to other researchers working within the field, both nationally and internationally. It may also be of interest to external stakeholders, such as relevant charities/initiatives and may also help inform policy.

V. Methods for data sharing

Summary data will be accessible through an open-access publication, which will include a Data Access statement. Research data and metadata will be deposited with the UK Data Service. The data will not be open-access but will be 'safeguarded,' ensuring that

researchers seeking to access the data will be bound by the terms of the UK Data Service End User Licence Agreement in addition to briefly justifying the reasons for their request. We will present our findings at national and international conferences and will engage with the University Press Office to create a press release if the findings are of significant public interest.

VI. Proprietary data

We do not anticipate that there will be any patentable data arising from this project.

VII. Timeframes

Data will be available to others following the publication of results. We will endeavour to review requests and grant access in a responsible and timely manner in line with the BBSRC Data Sharing Policy.

VIII. Format of the final dataset

The final dataset will not contain any identifiable information. Questionnaire data will be collated in a spreadsheet (.xls) and analysed using SPSS (.sav). Audio data will be stored short-term in .mp4 format but will be automatically transcribed using software and transcripts stored as .doc (or .csv) files, following quality control checks.